

국문 제목

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12-bit 1MSps SAR ADC for System-on-Chip

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Abstract

This paper proposes a 12-bit 1MSps SAR ADC (Successive Approximation Register Analog-to-Digital Converter) with low power consumption for SoC (System-on-Chip). The proposed circuit is designed using Magnachip/SK Hynix 0.18 μm CMOS 1Poly-6Metal process, and it is powered by 1.5 supply voltage. The proposed circuit in this paper showed high SNDR (Signal-to-Noise Distortion Ratio) of 71.18dB, and excellent ENOB (effective bit number of bits) of 11.53-bit as compared to conventional research results.

Index Terms: 12-bit, 1MSps, SAR, ADC, SoC

I. INTRODUCTION

The minimum length of a transistor decreases gradually evolved CMOS technology, accordingly, while reducing the supply

voltage and the area was able to integrate more functionality onto a single chip. Since it is possible to implement the analog block

to the digital block, a single chip is increasing the importance of the converter that converts an analog signal into a digital signal using analog-to-digital converter (ADC) [1-6].

II. Design of SAR ADC

Fig. 1 shows a block diagram of the proposed SAR ADC. This ADC contains Sample-and-Hold stage, capacitor array, SAR control logic stage, digital-to-analog converter (DAC), and DAC control logic. The optimization to minimize the size and power consumption for the complete block design was performed.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the result of Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) for the input signal of 80kHz. The proposed ADC showed high SNDR

(Signal-to-Noise Distortion Ratio) of 71.18dB, and excellent ENOB (effective bit number of bits) of 11.53-bit as compared to current research results.

Fig. 1. SAR ADC block diagram

Fig. 2. FFT result

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a 12-bit successive approximation register type 1MSps Analog-to-Digital converter is proposed. It contained ADC sample-and-hold stage, capacitor array, SAR control logic stage, DAC stage, and DAC control logic stage. The proposed ADC showed high SNDR (Signal-to-Noise Distortion Ratio) of 71.18dB and excellent ENOB (effective bit number of bits) of 11.53-bit as compared to conventional research results.

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